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Propagation of Leatherleaf Fern (*Rumohra adiantiformis*) from Rhizomes by In vitro Techniques

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Abstract

Among Floricultural plants, ornamental foliage plants have gained preference over flowering plants because; those plants can be used for a longer period of survival indoors. From them, ferns play a major role in the wholesale and retail florist business because of its popularity as ornamental plants and cut fronds. One of the most attractive ferns is the "leatherleaf fern" of family Dryopteridaceae. A novel micropropagation protocol for leatherleaf fern (*Rumohra adiantiformis* (G. Forst.) Ching) was successfully established using rhizomes as the explant. Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium containing 0.5 mg/L Kinetin (KIN), 1.0 mg/L 6-Benzylaminopurine (BAP) and 0.1 mg/L, 1-Naphthalene acetic acid (NAA) with 30 g/l sucrose was the most appropriate medium for culture initiation with the highest number of fronds (36) and rhizomes (20). *R. adiantiformis* cultures could be successfully proliferated using full-strength MS medium supplemented with 0.1 mg/L BAP, 0.1 mg/L NAA, 1.0 mg/L KIN and 0.1 mg/L BAP, 0.2 mg/l NAA, 1.0 mg/l KIN. Both hormonal combinations showed the highest proliferation rate (6.28) of regenerated rhizomes with no significant difference at $P \leq 0.05$. For commercial scale propagation of leather leaf fern, the treatment which contained 0.1 mg/l BAP, 0.1 mg/l NAA, 1.0 mg/l KIN was selected as the most suitable medium and the efficiency of the medium was observable from the first subculture through to the fourth subculture. The level of multiplication peaked in the fifth subculture and retained high quality until the sixth subculture. From the seventh *Rumohra adiantiformis* subculture onwards, the quality of regenerated fronds was reduced. Effective rooting was undertaken on 50% MS basal medium + glucose (15 g/L) + Ascorbic acid (100 mg/ L) and gelled with 0.8% (w/v) agar supplemented with NAA 1 mg/L with highest number of roots (6-8), 12-15 days after inoculation. All the acclimatized plantlets showed 100% survival percentage after 30 days.

Key words: In vitro propagation, Commercial scale, Leatherleaf fern, Rhizome culture

1. Introduction

Rumohra adiantiformis (G.Forst.) Ching, also known as the "leatherleaf" is highly valued on the international florist greenery market because of its long post-harvest display life (D'Souza et al., 2006). The cut foliage of leatherleaf is generally used in flower decorations as a filler, with year round availability and good display life (Reid, 2004; D'Souza et al., 2006). Generally, leatherleaf fern is propagated by dividing the root ball or rhizome and by germinating collected ripe spores. The former technique results in limited off-spring. Also, it is noted that when plant materials derived from rhizome splitting are used, which is usually usually followed by a reduction in the quality of fronds, increasing the susceptibility to disease, and causing an increase in the number of spores. The technique requires frequent replanting and makes it difficult to satisfy the increasing demand for fronds (Chen and Read, 1983; Strandberg, 2003). There is little research on the in vitro culture of *Rumohra adiantiformis* exists, and that which has been reported is mainly through rhizomes (Chen and Read, 1983) or spores (Brum and Randi, 2002). Thus following successful and repeatable *in vitro* propagation protocol for *Rumohra adiantiformis* was established in this study. The established protocol, used rhizomes as the explant material in optimized culture conditions, as well as ideal initiation, multiplication and rooting media. The plantlets produced from the study were successfully acclimatized *ex vitro* to produce fern plants commercially.

2. Materials & Methodology

2.1 Explant preparation

New rhizomes about 2 cm in length were collected from mother plants. The rhizomes were washed under running tap water. Rhizome scales were gently removed by hand after rinsing with distilled water for 3 times. Then the explants were washed with detergent Teepol for 5 minutes and kept under running tap water for 1 hour and surface sterilized with 20% Clorox for 10 minutes followed by 96% alcohol for 1 min. The disinfected explants were washed (3-4 washes) with sterile double distilled water to remove traces of sterilant. Rhizomes for the culture were prepared by slicing shoot tip area of descaled, sterilized rhizomes into 1.0–1.5 cm long segments. The entire cut rhizome segment was then cultured on medium, serving as the explant for culture initiation.

2.2 Culture initiation and multiplication

Full strength MS medium with 30 g/l sucrose and gelled with 0.8% (w/v) agar with pH adjusted to 5.8 was used as the basic medium and sterilized in an autoclave under 15 psi and 121°C. The medium was supplemented with combinations of Kinetin (KIN) (0, 0.25, 0.5 and 1.0 mg/L), 6-Benzylaminopurine (BAP) (1.0 mg/L) with either 1- Naphthalene acetic acid (NAA) (0.1mg/L) or NAA (0.2mg/L). To prevent browning of media activated charcoal (1g/L) and Ascorbic acid (100mg/L) were added to each medium combinations. Initially, to facilitate rhizome tip breaking and frond initialization dark conditions were supplied for 25 days. All cultures were incubated at 25±2°C with a 16/8 photoperiod under white fluorescent tubes during multiplication and rooting stages. Parameters observed in the experiments were percentage rhizome regeneration and the number of regenerated rhizomes. Percentage rhizome regeneration and a number of regenerated rhizomes were counted from the number of ex vitro rhizomes cultured from the point at which their tips broke and produced initial small fronds. Periodic observations were carried out to observe all alterations that might have occurred during incubation and all parameters were recorded 2 months after culture initiation.

For the multiplication of the cultures, sub culturing was started after 18 weeks and carried out six subcultures until no visible growth was observed in rhizomes. The cultures were sub cultured on the same composition of media and the length of each subculture was 6 weeks. The parameters recorded were a number of newly regenerated rhizomes/rhizome, number of fronds/rhizome, frond height (mm), number of roots/rhizome, and root length at every sub culturing stage.

2.3 *In vitro* rooting of micro-propagated shoots

Plantlets were prepared for acclimatization by splitting rooted rhizomes individually. The roots of individual rhizomes were cut using a culture blade and then cultured in half-strength MS medium supplemented with 0.1 mg/l NAA, 0.05 mg/l IBA, and 10 g/l sucrose to promote new roots. Each bottle consisted of 5 individual rhizomes. There were 20 bottles and these were incubated for 8 weeks in an incubation room with a 12-h photoperiod at 24±1°C under inflorescent lamps. After the two-month incubation period, well-rooted plantlets were used for acclimatization and the number of fronds/rhizome and the number of roots/rhizome were counted while frond height was measured for all plantlets.

2.4 Acclimatization of rooted rhizomes

For acclimatization rhizomes washed gently with Luke warm water and under running tap water to remove adhering agar. These plantlets were planted in trays containing sand, compost and coir dust in 1:1:1 ratio. These were kept in a shade house under high relative humidity (80–90 %). for acclimatization for 30 days and the percentage of survival was noted.

2.5 Experimental Design and Statistical analysis

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The experiment was arranged in a completely randomized design (CRD) with three replications. Each treatment consisted of 5 bottles and each bottle contained 3 explant clusters (each cluster containing two rhizomes). The parameters were subjected to analysis of variance and the means were compared with Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) at 95% significance level.

3. Results & Discussion

3.1 Culture initiation

Rhizome regeneration was begun when rhizome tips began to break and change from brown to pale yellow after culture initiation (Avila-Pérez et al. 2011), and it took 12-20 days for tip breaking after incubation in the dark. Obvious frond initials were observed 28–45 days. These new fronds became chlorophyllous after transferring to light conditions. More green fronds formation was observed after 2 months. The number of fronds and rhizomes produced at culture initiation stage was varied from 8 to 36 fronds/cluster and 1–20 rhizomes/cluster. The highest number of fronds (36) and rhizomes (20) was recorded on 0.5 mg/L KIN, 1.0 mg/L BAP with NAA 0.1mg/L.

3.2. Multiplication of regenerated rhizomes

The proliferation of regenerated rhizomes during multiplication was affected by the hormonal combinations in each medium. Different types of media for initiation culture using rhizome as the donor explant was successfully reported in *C. longa* with MS medium plus 2.5–3.0 mg/L of 2,4-D (Sunitibala et al., 2001), MS basal medium supplemented with 6 µM BA and 0.3 µM NAA, and 3% sucrose for *C. longa* (Islam et al., 2004), MS medium supplemented with 2.0 mg/l 2,4-D and 1.0 mg/L BA for *Polygonatum cyrtonema* (Zhao et al., 2003, 2009), and MS medium containing 0.2 mg/L NAA with 1 mg/l BA for *Alstromeria* cv. 'Jamaica' (Yousef et al., 2007).

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Plate 1. *In vitro* propagation of leather leaf fern. (a) Regenerated rhizome \pm 2 months after incubation in the light. (b) Regenerated and sliced tip rhizomes 2 months after the second subculture. (c and d) Growth and multiplied rhizomes. (e and f) Growing fronds of cultured tissue rhizomes. (g) Individual rhizome and root formation prepared for acclimatization. (h) Acclimatizing plantlets

Slow regeneration and multiplication of *in vitro* plants using rhizomes as the explant, generally reported in *Kaempferia galanga* (Swapna et al., 2004), were not seen in this study in which *R. adiantiformis* cultures could be successfully established using full-strength MS medium supplemented with 0.1 mg/L BAP, 0.1 mg/L NAA, 1.0 mg/L KIN and 0.1 mg/L BAP, 0.2 mg/L NAA, 1.0 mg/L KIN (Table 1). Both hormonal combinations showed the highest proliferation rate of regenerated rhizomes with no significant difference at $P \leq 0.05$. But when consider about commercial scale propagation of leatherleaf fern use of lower concentrations of hormones is economically feasible, therefore the treatment which contained 0.1 mg/l BAP, 0.1 mg/l NAA, 1.0 mg/l KIN was selected as the most suitable medium and the efficiency of the medium was observable from the first subculture through to the fourth subculture. Successful regeneration and multiplication were also reported for the same fern using Prague's medium containing 10 mg/l 2-iP and 10–15 mg/l KIN, 1 mg/l ZEA or 0.5 mg/l KIN (Chen and Read, 1983). High multiplication of regenerated shoots derived from rhizomes was established in *Acorus calamus* with MS medium containing 4 mg/l BA and 0.5 mg/l IAA (Rani et al., 2000), 1.5 mg/l BA and 0.2 mg/l NAA *Alstromeria* cv. 'Fuego' (Khaleghi et al., 2008), 2 mg/l 2,4-D and 1 mg/l BA for *P. cyrtonea* (Zhao et al., 2003, 2009), and 3 mg/L BA and 1 mg/L NAA for *Curcuma mangga* (Raihana et al., 2011). The medium regenerated on average up to 6.29 new rhizomes/rhizome with 18 fronds/rhizome, fronds 2.6 cm in height, 3.7 roots/rhizome and 1.82cm long roots (Table 1). The potential propagation from one culture cycle was 25.16 plantlets from one rhizome at four sub cultures, which was achieved within a short time.

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Table 1 Effect of different hormonal combinations on multiplication and growth of rhizomes.

Hormonal Combination (mg/L)			No. of new rhizomes/rhizome	No. of fronds /cluster	Frond height (cm)	No. of Roots/Rhizome	Root length (cm)
BAP	NAA	KIN					
0.1	0.1	0	0.92 ^g	6.54 ^g	1.6 ^a	4.3 ^c	1.70 ^e
0.1	0.1	0.25	1.81 ^e	8.26 ^f	1.4 ^a	4.5 ^c	1.80 ^c
0.1	0.1	0.50	3.21 ^c	11.50 ^d	1.7 ^a	5.6 ^b	1.86 ^a
0.1	0.1	1.00	6.29 ^a	17.90 ^a	2.6 ^a	3.7 ^d	1.82 ^{bc}
0.1	0.2	0	1.21 ^f	9.23 ^e	2.4 ^a	6.5 ^a	1.60 ^f
0.1	0.2	0.25	2.31 ^d	13.26 ^c	2.6 ^a	3.8 ^d	1.70 ^e
0.1	0.2	0.50	4.71 ^b	14.70 ^b	2.7 ^a	4.7 ^c	1.85 ^{ab}
0.1	0.2	1.00	6.28 ^a	18.03 ^a	2.8 ^a	3.5 ^d	1.78 ^d

Means followed by the same letter in the same column are not significantly different based on DMRT's test ($P \leq 0.05$).

Periodic subcultures had varied effects on shoot multiplication. In *Ananas comosus*, periodic subculture led to an increase in shoot formation until the third subculture and declined there-after (Hamad and Taha, 2008), shoot proliferation up to the third subculture of *Ceropegia intermedia* (Karuppusamy et al., 2009). Cell shape, cell surface, and the extracellular matrix changed and explants senesced, serving as indicators of reduced quality of regenerated rhizomes, and accompanied by smaller, thinner pale fronds. As many as 15–20 newly regenerated rhizomes formed by the second and third subculture, independent of culture conditions (Winarto & Teixeira 2012). It was observed that rhizomes could be multiplied by subsequent splitting and sub-culturing rhizome tips, resulting in the multiplication of fronds and the production of new rhizomes (Winarto & Teixeira da Silva 2012). After the third to fourth sub-culture root formation was initially observed. One explant cluster could produce 1–20 new rhizomes proliferation of new rhizomes peaked in number in the fifth subculture and gradually declined in subsequent subcultures (Figure 1). The growth of newly regenerated rhizomes peaked in the fifth subculture and that quality was maintained until the sixth subculture with an increase in frond height. Periodic subculture also successfully controlled browning of *Vitis vinifera* explants up to the third subculture (Jaskani et al., 2008), which was observable in our study also. However, in leatherleaf fern, a subculture of rhizomes periodically stimulated rhizome breaks, induced regeneration and multiplication of new rhizomes. Periodic subculture (i.e., every six weeks) of regenerated rhizomes stimulated newly regenerated rhizomes until the fourth subculture. High quality rhizomes could be obtained in the fourth and fifth subcultures, declining thereafter (Figure 1). This may be partly due to high cell density and exhaustion of growth factors in the medium at a high cell concentration (Freshney, 2006). Roots formed initially in the third subculture: their number and length increased in the next subculture. Furthermore, the quality of regenerated rhizomes was significantly reduced at the sixth subculture in which the fronds from rhizomes were thinner, and small in size.

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Figure 1 Multiplication rate of rhizomes in each subculture. Full-strength MS medium supplemented with M1-0.1 mg/l BAP, 0.1 mg/l NAA, 0 mg/l KIN, M2-0.1 mg/l BAP, 0.1 mg/l NAA, 0.25 mg/l KIN, M3- 0.1 mg/l BAP, 0.1 mg/l NAA, 0.5 mg/l KIN, M4-0.1 mg/l BAP, 0.1 mg/l NAA, 1.0 mg/l KIN, M5-0.1 mg/l BAP, 0.2 mg/l NAA, 0 mg/l KIN, M6-0.1 mg/l BAP, 0.2 mg/l NAA, 0.25 mg/l KIN, M7-0.1 mg/l BAP, 0.2 mg/l NAA, 0.5 mg/l KIN, M8-0.1 mg/l BAP, 0.2 mg/l NAA, 1.0 mg/l KIN

3.3 In vitro Rooting and Acclimatization

Effective rooting was undertaken on 50% MS basal medium + glucose (15 g/L) + Ascorbic acid (100 mg/L) and gelled with 0.8% (w/v) agar supplemented with NAA 1 mg/L with highest number of roots (6-8), 12-15 days after inoculation. Phenolic exudates cause browning and necrosis of plantlets and this was overcome by toting up the root induction medium with 100mg/L ascorbic acid. The plantlets with well-developed shoots and roots were transferred to poly bags for acclimatization. All the acclimatized plantlets showed 100% survival percentage after 30 days.

4.0 Conclusion

This study provides an efficient *in vitro* propagation method that could be commercially feasible for Leatherleaf Fern (*Rumohra adiantiformis*) from rhizomes, using a simple and cost-effective protocol for producing true to type plants in a relatively short period and with high multiplication rate. In summary, an *in vitro* propagation protocol for leatherleaf fern was successfully established. MS medium 0.5 mg/L Kinetin (KIN), 1.0 mg/L 6-Benzylaminopurine (BAP) and 0.1 mg/L, 1-Naphthalene acetic acid (NAA) with 30 g/l sucrose was the most appropriate medium for culture initiation, and MS medium supplemented with 0.1 mg/l BAP, 0.1 mg/l NAA, 1.0 mg/l KIN as the ideal multiplication medium for commercial scale multiplication of leather leaf fern. Consequently, well rooted rhizomes resulted in a high survival of rooted rhizomes (100%) *ex vitro*. Hence, this protocol is found to be optimal for the *in vitro* multiplication of the plant *Rumohra adiantiformis* to solve the commercialization and propagation bottle necks of this economically valuable foliage plant.

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